

A Note on the Kaufmann's Thiocyanogen Value of Indian Butter Fat (Ghee).

By U. D. BUDHALAKOTI AND K. C. MUKHERJI.

Some interesting results were published by Paul Arup regarding the Kaufmann's thiocyanogen and iodine values of some samples of butter obtained from Irish dairies (*Analyst*, 1932, 57, 610). He observed that the linolic acid content of the butter fats, as determined by the application of the thiocyanogen and iodine values, was fairly constant (3.3–4.6%) and could be relied on for finding out the purity of a sample of butter fat. The present work may be taken as a continuation of the above work and its aim was to determine how far this holds true in the case of Indian butter fats which are likely to differ largely in their chemical composition. N. N. Godbole and Sad Gopal have already estimated the percentage of oleic and linoleic acids in different oils and fats (including butter-fat) by this method. (*Allgem. & Fett. Ztg.*, 1934, 435). The process may also perhaps be adopted as an additional method for finding out the purity of samples of butter fat.

Authenticated samples of butter or butter fat were obtained from the following places:—

Dayalbagh Dairy, Agra.	1. Cow butter. 2. Buffalo butter.
Government Dairy, Bangalore.	1. Cow butter. 2. Buffalo butter.
Cawnpore Agricultural College Dairy, Cawnpore.	1. Cow butter fat. 2. Buffalo „ „
Keventer's Dairy, Aligarh.	1. Cow butter fat. 2. Buffalo „ „
Etawah Ghee Suppliers.	1. Ghee No. 1. 2. Ghee No. 2.

The samples of butter obtained as such were converted into fat by melting them in the air-oven at about 105° and decanting off the clear transparent fat and filtering. Before analysis all the samples of butter fat were dried in an air-oven at 105° – 110° for about 3 hours and cooled.

Method of Analysis.

Iodine value.—Wij's method as given in Lewkowitsch was followed.

Thiocyanogen value (Kaufmann's).—The following procedure was adopted, as given by Wizoff ("Einheitliche-untersuchungs Methoden für oöl und fett Industrie," 1930, II Auflage, p. 95).

400 C.c. of pure glacial acetic acid (Merck) were mixed with 40 c.c. of pure acetic anhydride and 120 c.c. of carbon tetrachloride (E. P.) and allowed to stand for a week. To half of the above solution 12.5 g. of pure lead sulphocyanide, prepared from lead acetate and potassium sulphocyanide and dried over phosphorus pentoxide for 15 days in the dark, were added and brought into suspension by shaking. To another half of the solution of glacial acetic acid and carbon tetrachloride, 3.2 c.c. of pure bromine (sp. gr. 3.188) was added. The bromine solution was then added to the suspended lead sulphocyanide little by little, each time shaking it vigorously till the colour of bromine was completely discharged. When all the bromine solution had thus been added and the bromine colour completely discharged, the solution was filtered through a previously dried filter paper. Precaution was taken at every step to exclude moisture. The clear colourless transparent solution, thus obtained, was used for the determination of thiocyanogen value in the same manner as is done in the case of Wij's iodine value.

0.2-0.3 G. of dried butter fat was taken in an iodine flask, 25-40 c.c. of thiocyanogen solution added, according to the quantity of fat taken. A blank was done exactly on similar lines. The reaction was allowed to proceed in the dark for 24 hours. An equal volume of 10% of KI solution was then added and the excess of thiocyanogen was titrated back with thiosulphate in terms of iodine liberated from potassium iodide.

The refractive indices were determined by the (Carl-Zeiss) Abbe refractometer. The various results obtained are tabulated below.

Serial No.	Description.		n_{40}° .	I_2 value.	SCN value.	Diff. between I_2 & SCN values.	Calc. linolic acid contents.	Remarks.
1.	Dayalbagh Dairy, Agra	Cow	1.4550	35.8	32.0	3.8	4.2%	
2.	Do	Buff	1.4550	37.6	34.4	3.2	3.5	Lowest linolic acid content.
3.	Government Dairy, Bangalore	Cow	1.4560	40.1	36.4	3.7	4.1	
4.	Do	Buff	1.4550	29.5	25.1	4.4	4.9	
5.	Agricultural College Dairy, Cawnpore	Cow	1.4570	49.9	45.0	4.9	5.4	Highest linolic acid content.
6.	Do	Buff	1.4560	40.4	36.8	3.6	4.0	
7.	Keventer's Dairy, Aligarh	Cow	1.4568	39.8	36.3	3.5	3.9	
8.	Do	Buff	1.4540	32.5	29.0	3.5	3.9	
9.	Etawah Ghee Suppliers	Ghee 1	1.4530	31.6	27.9	3.7	4.1	
10.	„	Ghee 2	1.4520	18.0	18.0	0.0	0.0	

(Note. Sample No. 10 is obviously *no butter-fat* at all but is most probably hydrogenated oil or fat sold as *Vegetable Ghee* both because of the R. I., I. V. and SCN values.)

The percentage of linolic acid content in the above table was found by multiplying the difference between the iodine value and thiocyanogen value by 1.104, which factor depends upon the fact that the unsaturated acids contained in butter fat are essentially oleic and linolic acids, and in the case of oleic acid, the iodine and thiocyanogen value is the same, while in the case of linolic acid the thiocyanogen value is half of that of the iodine value.

Let S = % saturated acids,
 O = % oleic acids, and
 L = % linolic acids.

We can have three equations as follows :—

1. $S + O + L = 100$
2. $OS + 0.899 O + 1.812 L = \text{Iodine value}$
3. $OS + 0.899 O + 0.906 L = \text{Thiocyanogen value.}$

From 2 and 3, we have

$$0.906 L = \text{Iodine value} - \text{thiocyanogen value.}$$

or $L = 1.104 (\text{Iodine value} - \text{thiocyanogen value}).$

SUMMARY.

1. The range of iodine value of different samples of butter fat is very wide (30-50) (Literature gives this as 25-47. Holde-Bleyberg, 7th edition, p. 802). (Katalenwasser-stoff öle and Fette.)

2. The linolic acid content of authenticated samples of butter fat is fairly constant and the range of variation comparatively very low (8.5-5.4).

3. One of the samples (No. 10) was found to contain no linolic acid and hence it is easy to conclude that the sample did not contain any butter-fat at all.

GENERAL RESEARCH SECTION,
H. B. TECHNOLOGICAL INSTITUTE, CAWNPORE,
UNITED PROVINCES.

Received March 3, 1935.

Putrefactive Decomposition of Bengal Silk Cocoon.

BY SIKHIBHUSHAN DUTT.

It is a well known fact that silk cocoon in presence of water undergoes decomposition very quickly and in the silk industry during the process of maceration of the cocoons in aqueous liquids for the removal of the yarn, very often a heavy odour of putrefaction is evolved, particularly if the temperature of the atmosphere is high. The products of such putrefaction have never been investigated by any one up to this time and although from the chemical point of view this would be quite interesting, yet the present investigation was undertaken from a slightly different standpoint. From a private communication from his friend Dr. V. N. Vyas of the King George's Medical College, Lucknow, the present author came to understand that the product of putrefaction of silk acted as a strong pressor substance for the heart, raising the blood pressure to a considerable extent. Apparently this must be due to the formation of some substances of great physiological activity during the process of putrefaction of silk cocoon and this was a sufficiently interesting field for research. Consequently the present investigation was undertaken with a view to elucidate the constitution of the compounds formed during the putrefaction.